

EXPLORING THE LANDSCAPE OF INNOVATION: A NETWORK-BASED APPROACH FOR VISUALIZING AND ANALYZING HETEROGENEOUS PATENT GRAPHS

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Abstract

This study presents a novel network-based methodology for exploring, visualizing, and analyzing patent data utilizing the Open Source Graph Visualization Tool Collaboration Spotting X (CSX). Through a transformative process, tabular patent data is converted into dynamic, heterogeneous graphs, providing a comprehensive view of the innovation landscape that is encoded in the patent data. This approach opens new avenues for understanding intricate relationships within technological ecosystems, offering insights into technological trends, innovation patterns, and the interconnectedness of inventors, institutions, and companies.

INTRODUCTION

Patents are considered a significant indicators of technological advancements as they are a rich, yet complex source of information. They encompass not only the details of the technological inventions they protect but also a wealth of related data, such as information about inventors, their affiliations, the evolution of intellectual property rights, and relationships between different patents.

However, effectively leveraging patent data for research or strategic decision-making is not a straightforward task. The data is often vast, multidimensional, and intricate in nature, thus posing substantial challenges for comprehensive analysis and understanding. Traditional approaches to patent analysis, which often focus on examining individual patents or simple aggregations of patent data, frequently fall short in revealing the complex, interrelated structures and emerging patterns within the patent landscape.

In response to these challenges, this research proposes a novel methodology for patent analysis that combines the power of network analysis and visual analytics, leveraging the capabilities of the Collaboration Spotting X (CSX) platform. This approach aims to transform raw, tabular patent data into dynamic, heterogeneous graphs that provide a comprehensive, visually intuitive view of the technological landscape. By doing so, it aspires to makes the understanding of innovation patterns and trends easier and enhance the accessibility of patent data.

The following sections will delve into the related works that inspired this approach, outline the conceptual underpinnings of this methodology, and highlight its potential contributions to the field of patent analysis and beyond.

RELATED WORK

In previous work of Yang et al. [1] the importance of visualization tools to enhance patent landscape analysis has been stressed. They propose the use of a tool to analyze and visualize patent data, thereby aiding in the identification of patterns and trends within large data sets. This study indicates the potential of visualization tools in patent analysis and the need for further development in this area.

Wittenburg et al. [2] further explores the importance of visualization tools for patent landscaping. The authors propose a novel tool that allows users to compare different technologies using multi-dimensional comparative visualization. This tool provides an interactive environment where users can manipulate the display to understand and compare different technology fields. The findings in this paper underpin the significance of interactive visualization in patent landscape analysis and its potential to enhance understanding and decision-making.

CONCEPT

The proposed methodology centers on transforming the complex, tabular patent data into a visually insightful and analytically rich heterogeneous graph using CSX. Inventors, institutions, companies, and other patent data elements are represented as nodes, with their interconnections depicted as edges. This transformation process uncovers hidden patterns and relationships within the patent data, resulting in an intuitive visual representation. In a first step patent data is extracted from the big amount of patent data that is available so that it can fit into a tabular dataset. In a second step data is transformed in the CSX platform into heterogenous graphs for analysis.

The CSX platform offers dynamic exploration capabilities, allowing users to interact with the generated graphs, adjust visualization parameters, and explore different perspectives of the data. This interactive approach enables a deeper understanding of the innovation landscape, facilitating the discovery of technological trends, key innovators, collaboration networks, and competitive landscapes.

This research's novelty lies in its innovative application of CSX for the visualization and analysis of patent data, introducing a new dimension to patent analysis. Furthermore, by offering an interactive and dynamic exploration of the innovation landscape, it paves the way for strategic decision-making in technology development and innovation management.

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